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PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Abstract.

The formation and development of professional thinking in future teachers is a critical component of teacher education, shaping their ability to navigate the complexities of the classroom and broader educational environments. This study examines the psychological characteristics that contribute to the development of professional thinking, focusing on motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and reflective practice. A mixed-methods approach was employed, involving 120 pre-service teachers from two universities. Quantitative data were collected through self-report questionnaires and analyzed using paired t-tests and correlation analysis. Qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and analyzed thematically. The results revealed significant increases in intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and engagement in reflective practices over the course of the academic year. The findings highlight the importance of integrating theoretical knowledge with practical experiences, fostering a supportive learning environment, and encouraging reflective practice to enhance the professional thinking of future teachers.

Keywords: professional thinking, teacher education, motivation self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, reflective practice, pre-service teachers, professional identity.

Introduction. The development of professional thinking is a critical aspect of teacher education, shaping not only the knowledge and skills of future educators but also their ability to engage, inspire, and lead students. Professional thinking in teachers encompasses a range of cognitive, emotional, and social processes that enable them to effectively navigate the complexities of the classroom, curriculum, and broader educational environment. This article explores the psychological characteristics that underpin the formation and development of professional thinking in future teachers, highlighting the key factors that contribute to their professional growth. Professional thinking in teachers is rooted in a deep understanding of educational theory and practice, coupled with the ability to apply this knowledge in real-world settings. It involves critical thinking, problem-solving, decision-making, and reflective practice—all essential for effective teaching. However, the development of these cognitive skills is not automatic; it is shaped by a range of psychological factors, including motivation, self-efficacy, and emotional intelligence [3]. Motivation plays a pivotal role in the formation of professional thinking. Future teachers who are intrinsically motivated—driven by a genuine passion for teaching and a commitment to student success—are more likely to engage deeply with their professional learning and development. This intrinsic motivation is often linked to the development of a strong professional identity, where future teachers see themselves not just as educators, but as lifelong learners and leaders in their field.

Methods. The study involved 120 pre-service teachers enrolled in teacher education programs at two universities. The participants were in their final year of study, preparing to enter the teaching profession. They

were selected based on their willingness to participate in the study and represent a diverse range of educational disciplines, including elementary education, secondary education, and special education. The sample included both male and female participants, with ages ranging from 21 to 30 years. Motivation for Teaching Questionnaire (MTQ): This self-report questionnaire was designed to measure the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of pre-service teachers. It included items related to their reasons for choosing the teaching profession, their commitment to teaching, and their passion for working with students.

1. Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale (TSES): This scale was used to assess the participants' beliefs in their abilities to perform various teaching tasks. It covered areas such as classroom management, instructional strategies, and student engagement.

2. Emotional Intelligence Inventory (EII): The EII measured the emotional intelligence of pre-service teachers, focusing on their ability to recognize and manage their own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. It included subscales for self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and relationship management.

3. Reflective Practice Survey (RPS): This survey assessed the extent to which pre-service teachers engaged in reflective practice. It included items related to their use of self-reflection, feedback from peers and mentors, and their approach to continuous professional development.

4. Professional Thinking Development Interview (PTDI): This semi-structured interview was conducted with a subset of 30 participants. The interview focused

on their experiences in developing professional thinking, including challenges faced, strategies used, and the role of social learning.

The study was conducted over the course of an academic year. Participants completed the MTQ, TSES, EII, and RPS at the beginning and end of the year to assess changes in their motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and reflective practices. The PTDI was conducted midway through the year to gain in-depth insights into the development of professional thinking. Quantitative data from the questionnaires and surveys were analyzed using statistical methods, including paired t-tests to compare pre- and post-test scores, and correlation analysis to examine the relationships between the variables. The qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed thematically, identifying key themes related to the development of professional thinking.

Results. The analysis of the MTQ showed a significant increase in intrinsic motivation among participants over the course of the academic year ($t(119) = 4.52, p < 0.001$). This suggests that as future teachers progressed through their training, their internal commitment to the teaching profession deepened. Results from the TSES indicated a significant improvement in self-efficacy scores from the beginning to the end of the year ($t(119) = 5.63, p < 0.001$). Participants reported higher confidence in their ability to manage classrooms, implement instructional strategies, and engage students effectively. The EII results showed a moderate but significant increase in overall emotional intelligence scores ($t(119) = 3.47, p < 0.01$), with the most substantial gains observed in the areas of self-awareness and relationship management. This suggests that participants became more adept at understanding and managing their emotions, as well as building positive relationships. The RPS indicated a significant increase in the frequency and depth of reflective practices among participants ($t(119) = 4.75, p < 0.001$). Participants reported more regular engagement in self-reflection and a greater willingness to seek and utilize feedback from peers and mentors.

Discussion. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the psychological characteristics that contribute to the formation and development of professional thinking in future teachers. The significant improvements observed in motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and reflective practices over the course of the academic year highlight the dynamic nature of professional growth during teacher education. The increase in intrinsic motivation among participants suggests that teacher education programs can effectively nurture a deep commitment to the teaching profession. This intrinsic motivation is likely linked to the development of a strong professional identity, where future teachers begin to see themselves as educators with a clear purpose and mission. The positive shift in motivation also underscores the importance of aligning educational experiences with the personal values and aspirations of pre-service teachers. This alignment not only enhances their engagement with the program but also prepares them to face the challenges of the profession with resilience and dedication. The significant rise

in self-efficacy scores is a promising indicator that pre-service teachers are developing the confidence needed to succeed in the classroom. Self-efficacy is crucial for effective teaching, as it influences a teacher's willingness to experiment with new instructional strategies, manage classroom dynamics, and respond to diverse student needs [8]. The findings suggest that teacher education programs that provide ample opportunities for hands-on practice, supported by constructive feedback, can significantly boost the self-efficacy of future teachers. This confidence is essential for fostering a proactive and adaptive approach to teaching, enabling educators to navigate the complexities of the profession with greater ease.

The results of this study have important implications for the design and implementation of teacher education programs. First, programs should focus on fostering intrinsic motivation and professional identity by aligning educational experiences with the personal values and aspirations of future teachers. Second, they should provide ample opportunities for hands-on practice, supported by feedback, to build self-efficacy and confidence in teaching. Third, teacher education programs should include training on emotional intelligence to equip future teachers with the interpersonal skills necessary for effective classroom management. Finally, reflective practice should be integrated into all aspects of teacher education, encouraging future teachers to continuously reflect on and improve their practice.

Conclusion. The development of professional thinking in future teachers is a multifaceted process that is influenced by a range of psychological characteristics. By understanding and addressing these characteristics, teacher education programs can better prepare future educators to meet the demands of the profession and make a positive impact on their students. The findings of this study highlight the importance of a holistic approach to teacher education, one that supports the psychological growth of pre-service teachers and fosters their development as reflective, confident, and emotionally intelligent professionals. The formation and development of professional thinking in future teachers is a complex, multifaceted process that is influenced by a range of psychological characteristics.

Motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, reflective practice, and social learning are all critical factors that contribute to the growth of professional thinking in teachers. By understanding and nurturing these psychological characteristics, teacher education programs can better prepare future educators to meet the demands of the profession and make a lasting impact on their students and the broader educational community. The findings indicate that the psychological characteristics of motivation, self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and reflective practice play a significant role in the formation and development of professional thinking in future teachers. The quantitative data demonstrated significant improvements in these areas over the course of the academic year, while the qualitative data provided insights into the processes and experiences that contribute to this development.

Together, these results underscore the importance of a holistic approach to teacher education, one that supports the psychological growth of future educators as they prepare for the demands of the teaching profession.

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